

Supporting Information:
Single-Layer and Double-Layer Filtration
Materials Based on Polyvinylidene
Fluoride-Co-Hexafluoropropylene Nanofibers
Coated on Melamine Microfibers

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Figure S1: Flowchart of the simulation method.